

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B196
Date: 10 May 2006
Take Off: 10:47:46
Landing: 15:31:46
Flight Time: 4h44m00s

Campaign: CAESAR
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: SW approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Andreas Keil	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud physics/ccm2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
7	Mission Scientist 2	Stuart Newman	Met Office
8	AVAPS/CVI/CCM2	Paul James	Met Office
9	Core Chem	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
10	ARIES 1	Alan Vance	Met Office
11	MARSS DEIMOS	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
12	CAA	Nick Butcher	Met Office
13	ARIES 2	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
14	CAA2	Janice Fisher	Met Office
15	IR camera	Joss Kent	Met Office
16	CCN1	Bruce Giddings	Met Office
17	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met office
18	Flight Experience 3	Jeff Brown	Met office
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B196 Track 10-MAY-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b196
 Date: 10/5/06
 Project: NEON
 Location: Suffolk and offshore

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
103547		inu to nav	0.16 kft	126	
103622		engine start	0.16 kft	126	
103918		power change	0.16 kft	126	
104021		taxy	0.16 kft	126	start
104746		T/O	0.18 kft	035	
104922		ASP	2.2 kft	029	open
111701	112934	Profile 1	11.0 - 0.16 kft	229	
113434	113501	Run 1.1	0.52 - 0.65 kft	048	hall
113914	113938	Run 1.2	0.58 - 0.60 kft	227	
114601	114648	Run 2.1	1.1 kft	031	abeam rway end
115259	115332	Run 2.2	1.1 kft	216	abeam rway end
115359	115548	Profile 2	1.2 - 3.1 kft	256	
120016	120049	Run 3.1	3.1 kft	025	
120136	120345	Profile 3	3.1 - 5.1 kft	054	
120817	120857	Run 4.1	5.1 kft	203	
121449	121522	Run 4.2	5.1 - 5.2 kft	031	
121553	121900	Profile 4	5.2 - 8.1 kft	047	
122405	122448	Run 5.1	8.1 kft	199	
122759		video	8.1 kft	022	tapes change
123204	123319	Run 5.2	8.1 kft	195	
123625	123827	Profile 5	8.1 - 10.0 kft	038	
124708		Sonde 1	10.0 kft	048	
125412	131336	Profile 6	9.9 - 0.15 kft	228	
125740		Profile 6	7.2 kft	227	interrupt
130444		Profile 6	7.1 kft	236	resume
131940	132007	Run 6.1	0.60 kft	048	
132526	132552	Run 6.2	0.62 - 0.63 kft	228	
132608	132733	Profile 7	0.64 - 2.2 kft	227	
140115		Video	1.9 kft	157	tapes change
142244	143245	Run 7.1	0.01 - -.07 kft	345	
143443	144446	Run 8.1	-.04 - 0.00 kft	121	
144631	145632	Run 9.1	0.07 - 0.08 kft	298	
145659	150700	Run 10.1	0.01 - 0.05 kft	301	
152305		ASP	7.0 kft	176	closed
153146		Land	0.19 kft	212	
153542		standstill	0.19 kft	311	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B196 Track 10-MAY-06

SORTIE BRIEF - NEON

Flight B196

10 May 2006

Trial Objectives

1. To validate the NEON TDA using the IR camera system in cloud free conditions looking at a runway.
2. Measure infra-red signature of a large ship with the IR camera.

Take off

11:30 a.m. local time

Location

1. Over and nearby the runways of Wattisham Airfield.
2. Over the North Sea.

Weather

1. Ideally: Totally cloud free conditions, flights around lunch time
2. Cloud-free is preferred, but not essential

Instrumentation Required

IR camera, core temperature, water vapour, ARIES, aerosol instruments (PCASP)

Special Conditions

Note that in order to keep the runway in the field of view of the IR camera all altitudes will need to be flown at exact heights above the surface and NOT at flight levels.

Flight Pattern (see Fig. 1)

1. Take off and transit to Wattisham Airfield, to arrive at 10,000ft.
--- Wattisham Airfield -----
 2. 1st PROFILE = descent at 1,000ft/min to minimum altitude with a missed approach at the operating airfield
 3. 1st HAL (see Fig. 2) = runs at 500ft, sequence: over and along runway, loop, displaced to runway over grass path next to runway; note special needs for ARIES and Heimann
 4. 20-degree approaches (see Fig. 3), i.e. straight and level runs at 1000ft, 3000ft, 5000ft, and 10,000ft (getting the runway into the field of view of the IR camera)
 5. 2nd PROFILE (identical to point 2, also with missed approach at the operating airfield)
 6. 2nd HAL
--- North Sea -----
 7. Search a larger ship flying over the North Sea (e.g. a ferry near Harwich)
 8. Close up to the ship to take IR cam pictures
 9. Fly at altitudes of 1000, 3000, 5000 and 10000ft above the ship, thereby getting the ship + the ship wake in the field of view of the IR camera

 10. Transit back.
 11. If time allows: 20-degree approach at 10,000ft (+5,000ft) over Cranfield runway.
 12. Landing.
- Total time: about 4h 30 min (= 270mins).**

NEON Sortie

V/P = "fast" vertical profile
M/A = missed approach over runway
HAL = "Heimann-ARIES loop"

Fig. 1: NEON sortie Height vs. Time. It includes:

- Two vertical profiles (scientific flying) ending with missed approaches
- Two "HALs" (cp. Fig. 2) to take place at 500ft height.
- Several "20-degree approaches" (cp. Fig. 3) at 1000, 3000, 5000, and 10,000ft.

NEON flights: Tasks + Sortie

(April-May 2006)

1. General:

- Primary Goal: To measure the IR signature of a runway and its surroundings (e.g. nearby grass paths) with the IR camera
- Secondary Goal: To take IR camera pictures of a large ship and the corresponding ship wake
- Flight hours: Up to 3 flights of 4.5 hours duration (or more flights of shorter duration)

2. Flight planning:

a. Weather:

- The flights should take place in clear-skies and around noon to allow for a maximum contrast between the targets

b. Locations

Over and nearby the runways of:

- Wattisham Airfield, or
- RAF St Mawgan (preferred if ship measurements added into sortie).

c. Instrumentation

- IR camera (incl. spotter camera), core temperature, water vapour, ARIES, Heimann, [SWS], PCASP, Nephelometer, PSAP, dropsondes
- The IR camera will look to the left, most likely 35 degrees below the horizontal. It will be in the DEIMOS position, housed in the forward bay of the large radiometer blister on the port side of the aircraft.

d. Sortie summary:

- See Fig. 1 for sortie profile and Figures 2 and 3 for special flying hints. Sorties will consist of runs at about 5 exact heights (not flight levels!) between 500 ft and 10.000 ft above ground, and will include one or two missed approaches over the runway (to get the full vertical profile of met and aerosol parameters).

3. Check list:

a. Pre-Flight:

- Fit lens into IR camera that gives a Field of View FoV of 11 degrees. For a pure ship & ship wake flight potentially experiment with FoV=45 deg.
- Set IR camera to view 35 degrees below the horizontal. [If the IR camera cannot be at 35 degrees below the horizontal, re-calculate horizontal displacement distances with online EXCEL Height-Distance Converter using the exact actual angle].
- Calibration of the IR camera! (ask Joss!)

b. In-Flight:

- Ask St Mawgan or Wattisham airfield for visibility at ground! (needed for NEON model input)

- If possible, have a sonde dropped near the runway (e.g. over the sea near St. Mawgan).
- ARIES to look in same direction as IR camera and at 16cm-1 resolution during the whole flight, in particular during the 20-degree approach runs. This is different for the Heimann-ARIES loops (see HAL description later on).

c. Post-Flight:

Instant data gathering of:

- IR camera data!
- Met data (humidity, temp) + visibility at ground
- ARIES

4. Support Material:

The following can be found via <http://metresearch.net/CAESAR/> :

- This sortie brief (up-dated versions)
- NEON Height-Distance Converter (EXCEL sheet)
- PowerPoint presentation on NEON sortie

5. Extra Tasks:

a. Ship & Ship Wakes:

- As an important secondary task the IR signature of a ship should be measured with the IR camera. It should be a big ship, e.g. a large container ship or a ferry, and flying should be done as close as possible to the ship.
- Also the ship wake should be recorded with the infra-red camera. This should be done at various flight heights, ideally: 1000, 3000, 5000, 10000 and 14000ft.

Potential areas to do this “ship chasing” could be the Channel or sea areas near Bristol port, in particular when added onto the runway sortie over St. Mawgan. Experience from the runway as well as “trial-and-error” approaches should be used to find the best way to actually get the ship and the ship wake in the FoV of the IR camera. ARIES should be run at 16cm-1 resolution, same direction as IR camera. There is no need for cloud-free conditions for these tasks!

b. Additional:

As these are the first flights of the IR camera over the UK (i.e. still test phase), the flight pattern can be varied by the mission scientist to contribute to and expand the objective. For instance:

- If approached by a Tornado aircraft arrangements could be made to get the Tornado in the FoV of the IR CAMERA;
- Try to get other interesting objects (e.g. bunkers, large concrete areas) nearby the runway in the field of view, ideally from 3,000ft height
- Fly additional anti-clockwise orbits around the runway, thereby keeping the runway in the field of view;
- E.g. during the transit back, targets providing potentially decent contrasts could be over-flown, e.g. coastlines (land vs. sea), towns, motorways, etc.; just keep the IR camera recording switched on.

HAL (Heimann-ARIES loop)

- ARIES down (max. resolution), Heimann measuring
- - - ARIES up, Heimann calibration

ARIES calibration before and after HAL

Fig. 2: "Heimann-ARIES loop" (top view).

"20-degree approach" - top view -

Flights along runway with about 20 deg angle to make sure to get runway in FoV of the IR camera ! (ala Joss' Africa Experience)

Fig. 3: "20 degree approach" instead of flying parallel to the runway to get runway in FoV of the IR cam.

Appendix A: Height – Distance Conversion

The horizontal shift S of flight legs parallel to the runway to keep the runway in the view of the IR camera is dependent on the angle Y the camera is looking below the horizontal and the flight height H:

$$S \text{ (nautical miles)} = H \text{ (ft)} / \tan(Y) * 0.3048 * 0.54E-03$$

Assuming IR camera view = 35 degrees down the horizontal:

(Use EXCEL sheet to compute distances for other angles, <http://metresearch.net/CAESAR/>)

Ideal NEON flight levels marked with an X	Flight Height (ft)	Displacement right of runway (nautical miles)	Flight Height (km)	Displacement (km)	Displacement (statute miles)	IR camera viewing distance (km)
missed approach: X	0	0	0	0	0	0
X	500	0.118	0.152	0.218	0.135	0.12
X	1000	0.235	0.305	0.435	0.270	0.53
	2000	0.470	0.610	0.871	0.541	
X	3000	0.705	0.914	1.306	0.811	1.59
	4000	0.940	1.219	1.741	1.082	
X	5000	1.175	1.524	2.176	1.352	2.66
	6000	1.410	1.829	2.612	1.623	
	7000	1.645	2.134	3.047	1.893	
	8000	1.880	2.438	3.482	2.164	4.25
	9000	2.115	2.743	3.918	2.434	
X	10000	2.350	3.048	4.353	2.705	5.31
	12000	2.821	3.658	5.224	3.246	
(X)	14000	3.291	4.267	6.094	3.787	7.44
	27000	6.346	8.230	11.753	7.303	

Table 1: Displacement for straight and level runs to keep the runway in the FoV of the IR camera (Y=35 degrees).

Fig. 4: Displacement graph (Y=35 degrees).

Appendix B: Instructions for Instrument Operators

1. IR camera

- Get runway in FoV of the IR camera during the 20-degree approaches (cp. Fig. 3), check using spotter camera. If this fails, run must be repeated!
- Record both, IR camera and spotter camera pics.

2. Heimann

- Heimann to be working during HALs (Heimann-ARIES loops), Heimann calibration during up-view of ARIES

3. ARIES

- Record every interferogram, i.e. no co-averaging!
- During the whole flight, in particular the 20-degree approaches, look in same direction as IR cam, i.e. 55 degrees up (=35 deg below the horizontal) and to the left AND use 16cm-1 resolution

HAL (cp. Fig. 2):

- During HAL → maximum resolution!
- HAL: over runway or grass → ARIES to look down
- HAL: away from runway/grass path → ARIES to look up
- ARIES calibration before and after HALs

4. SWS

- To be switched on during HALs and 1,000ft levelling
- Always looking straight down, offset roll & pitch

Mission Scientist Debrief

B196 10th May 2006

NEON flight over Wattisham Airfield and North Sea

Mission Scientist: Andreas Keil

Weather Conditions:

Clear sky throughout the flight. A very pronounced (humid, polluted) boundary layer with top heights of about 3000ft; the haze within this made it difficult to spot ships from higher altitudes when “ship hunting” over the North Sea.

Sortie:

NEON Sortie

1. “runway profiling” for NEON

A NEON sortie over and nearby the runway of Wattisham Airfield was performed as planned in the sortie brief with the only exception of the 20-degree approach at 10,000 ft which could not be performed due to flight restrictions and therefore was substituted by an approach at 8,000ft (only the edge of the runway was captured by the IR cam here).

2. “ship hunting” for NEON

It was tried to capture IR camera images of ships when flying over the North Sea. The altitudes for this ship hunt were 5000ft (practically without success), 2000ft (one ship captured), and 1000ft (several ships captured).

3. MARSS over sea

Eventually, to test MARSS, straight and level runs were performed at FL50, 150, 250 (10 min. each) and 200 (6 min.).

Instrument status:

Everything OK apart from:

- ARIES: Not working for the first part of the flight, including the 1st HAL, OK afterwards.

Learning:

- There is an urgent need to have the spotter camera picture recorded simultaneously with IR camera recording.
- The 11 deg lens in the IR cam is not suitable for “ship hunting”, use 45 deg lens if possible!; Getting the runway in the field of view of the IR cam is difficult (but possible) at altitudes above 5000ft when using the 11 deg lens; Using the 32 deg lens for the IR cam should be the ideal middle solution if “runway profiling” and “ship hunting” are to be done in one and the same sortie ...
- Summarizing the needs for IR cam lens use:
 - Runway profiling → 11 deg lens
 - Ship hunting → 45 deg lens
 - Combination of runway profiling and ship hunting → 32 deg lens

Mission Scientist's Summary Report

Andreas Keil

1. Overview

Date of Flight: 10 May 2006
Location: Over Wattisham Airfield & over North Sea
Duration: 5 hours (4.5 hours NEON + ½ hour for MARSS)

2. Objectives achieved

A. NEON sortie over Wattisham runway

- full sortie realized as in sortie brief: 2 HALs at 500ft, 2 vertical profiles to the airfield, 2 missed approaches, 20-deg approaches to runway (runway in FOV of IR cam) at 1000ft, 3000ft, 5000ft, (8000ft).
- clearly separated boundary layer (about 3000ft top height): very moist (90% RH, 7-8 g/kg), relatively high aerosol load.
- [IR cam also switched on during some bits of horizontal flights over land]

B. Ship Hunting over North Sea

- 5000 ft: some missed attempts, 1 impressive ship wake, 1 “half ship”
- 2000 ft: some missed attempts, 1 ship wake
- 1000 ft: several successful approaches to ships getting ships and/or ship wakes in the FOV of the IR cam.
- In general ship wakes appeared brownish in the visible, being rather small in horizontal extent.

C. MARSS testing over North Sea

- SLR were performed at 100, 150, 250 ft (10 min. each) as well as at 200 ft (6min.)

3. Problems

For A.:

- ARIES not working during 1st half of flight, including first HAL
- we got no clearance to fly at 10,000 feet over the runway, therefore had to opt for 8,000ft (only short edge look at runway from that height)

For B.:

- ship hunting at 2000 and 5000 ft altitude difficult with the 11 deg lens employed in IR cam

4. Further needs/improvement suggestions

- Ship hunting to be done with larger FOV in IR cam, ideally 45 deg. Possibly combination of runway and ship measurements with 32 deg lens.
- General: Due to Wattisham flight restrictions St. Mawgan is the option with more freedom for undisturbed flying.

NEON (+MARS)

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Keil
M/SZ

V₀ 11:30 local

Flight No **B.196**
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Date **10/5/06**

Page **1** of **2**

Local (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:47:48		0		Completed	TAKE OFF / 7°C / 88 kts
10:49					IR shutter opened, strong!
10:55					DW + FW fairly common, some started
10:55					A runway in IR FOV!
10:57:07					! First in IR camera! recorded
11:04		11k			11kft → 500 cm ² PCASP
11:09:36					→ several streaks + traffic + fields in IR camera
11:09:36					own air takes with IR. Rare
11:12:00					Coastline! in view (IR shut)
11:17:01		11k			Profile #1 started → IR
11:28:20					IRON (off in between)
11:29:35		50	(10)	Wattish	M/A 1
11:34:35		30 sec			over runway / ARIES dead!
11:35:20		500			runway in FOV, 500ft / over grass
11:38					up to 3500 cm ² near ground
11:40		1000			1000ft failed 20° - A
11:53		1000			runway in FOV
12:01		3000			runway in FOV
12:09		5000			failed
12:15:30		5000			runway in FOV, only 2 short!
12:24		8k			runway in FOV (short)
12:33		8k			(ground in FOV (only little edge))
12:37					[Mission ended! Wrap] Sta → Anders

HAL

NEON (+ MARS)

Aircraft Scientist's Log

VEIL
M/S 1

Flight No **B. 196**.....

Date 10/5/06.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:47		10,000		19/52.7	SONDE DROPPED
12:53		10,000		North Sea	2 nd PROFILE started
12:57:40		7,000			- interrupt profile at 7000 ft - - waiting loop -
13:04:44		7,000			resume profile / pronounced SL height at ≈ 2500 ft
13:14		50		WATWIK	M/A 2
13:20		500		"	over runway
13:25		500		"	over grass path
					Waltham finished / DONE!
			(2)		Ship chasing
					climb to 5,000 ft
over	1	5000 ft		over	1/2 ship
13:47		"		North	+ 1 ship wake (without ship)
after		2000 ft		sea	1 wake
13:56		4		(shallow water)	
14:05		200 ft			good one! (Photos taken from cockpit)
14:20					wakes + ships
END					(tankers + other) / DONE!
			(3)		MARSS
14:22:44	stat	100 ft		over	three 10-minute
14:34:43	stat	150 ft		North	SL runs for MARSS
14:46:31	stat	250 ft		Sea	(+ 6 minutes at 200 ft) / DONE!
15:07:00	stat				Transit back starts
15:35					LANDING

Total flight time: **45h.**

10/5/06 / *[Signature]*

Aircraft Scientist's Log

S.M. NEWMAN

Flight No **B.196**.....
FAAM © 2004

Date **10/8/2006**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
104745					TAKE-OFF
1059					Hazy in transit
1103	—	FZ110	067	52 ³⁶ 0 ⁴⁸ E	500/CC PCASP observed
111701	P1	FZ110 ↓	237	52 ²⁴ 1 ³⁶ E	Visibility not great, but totally clear sky
1129	end P1	50 feet			missed approach, Heilmann 55 ⁵⁸ $\sim 30^{\circ}\text{C}$ +
113434	R1.1	500'	049	52 ⁰⁰ 0 ⁵⁴ E	H. Tx $\sim 30^{\circ}\text{C}$ over runway
113814	R1.2	"			H. Tx $\sim 31.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ offset runway to R.
" 38	end R1.2				* ARIES not working * (over grass)
114801	R2.1	1000'	028	52 ⁰⁰ 0 ⁵⁴ E	max 3500 counts at low level from PCASP
					Too far away for IR camera 100% clear sky
115259	R2.2	1000'	208	52 ¹² 1 ⁰⁰ E	repeat 1000' leg
115548 end	P2	1000 \uparrow 3000			2800' seems to be cut-off for aerosol concentrations, much larger below this
120016	R3.1	3000'			Heilmann $\sim 20^{\circ}\text{C}$
120049	end	"			
120136	P3	5000 ^{up to 5000} '	053	52 ¹² 1 ¹² E	still hazy, clear
120345	end				
120817	R4.1	5000'	205	52 ⁶ 0 ⁵⁴ E	
" 57	end	"			Missed with IR camera, so re-doing
121449	R4.2	"	051	52 ⁰ 0 ⁵⁴ E	
	end	"			Successful images with IR camera
121900 end	P4	8000 ^{up to 8000} '			No clearance to F100, so F1080
122405	R5.1	8000'	206	52 ⁰⁶ 0 ⁵⁴ E	T -0.9°C Td -8°C
	end	"			ARIES missed some data, so re-doing
123204	R5.2	"	195	52 ⁶ 0 ⁵⁴ E	
	end	"			

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.196**
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 Date **10/5/2006**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	
125412	R6↓				(Andreas takes over as M.Sci. at front)	
					aborted due to air traffic	
130444	R6rec.	700ft↓	226	52°18' 124°E		
	end	at soft			missed approach	
131940	R6.1	500ft	040	52°0' 148°E	"Helina ARLES Loop" T 17°C Td 80c	
132502ad	R6.2	"	227			
	PA	200ft				
1341		5000'			Looking for ships/wakes) in IR camera	
1345					Calm sea state	
1400		2000'		52°18' 148°E	Closer chasing of ships	
1404	R↓	1000'		52°12' 148°E	Even closer, v. calm sea	
1405					Good view of ship in IR camera	
1412					Ship wake is muddy, indicating how shallow water is	
1419					Conclusion of ship meas, now MARSS at low level	
142244	R7.1	100'			MARSS+ mainly nadir ARLES meas.	
143245	end	"			(oriented around Norfolk coast N'wards)	
143443	R8.1	150'			(oriented S/E wards)	
144446	end	"			} all clear sky	
144631	R9.1	250'				(oriented N/W wards)
145632	end	"				
145659	R10.1	200'				(still W'wards)
150700	end					
1532					LAND	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B196

Location: No

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Date: 10-5-6

Operator(s): VANCE / TIDEMAN

Resolution: 1816

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
	preflight	B196B	C	42	31	19	-190	23	IR	Testing 50s. scan. 1cm ⁻¹ !!
0926	↓	B196C							90s → save & data error - Restart,	
		D							IR @ 16cm ⁻¹	1sec scan
		E							--	~ 45 total.
		F							--	6sec / 45
		G							SLASH	1:11, try 700 "data error"
1008		H							--	write error.
1012		I							RESTARTING PC	
		J							slash	30 sec. / write error.
		K							IR FAST (16cm ⁻¹)	10 sec. meas. 1k tot.
		L							IRN 45	— wrong res.!
102530	M							-- (1cm ⁻¹)	write error	
1029	N							N1	OK	
	O							IRN45	write error	
	P							--	"	
103531	Q							--	OK for 10 IGMS.	
	R								WRITE ERROR	

TESTING ↓

230

irn 45

ir - fast

ARIES flight log

Flight: B196

Location: waltisham

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Date: 10/5/06

Operator(s): TIPPENAW / VANCE

Resolution: 16 cm⁻¹

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
120735				71	31				CHIX1	
121925	S+L	C196A	C	71	31	15	-190	26	CHIX1	16 cm ⁻¹ Res 24/s
122053		C196B	C	71	31	14	-190	26	CHIX1	
122250		C196C	C	71	31	14	-190	26	CHIX1	
122440		C196D	C	71	31	12	-190	25	ir - fast	
122757		C196E	C	71	31	11	-191	24	CHIX1	
123230		C196F	C	71	31	10	-190	26	ir - fast	
1240										Set to 1 cm ⁻¹ 4/s
125901		C196G	C	71	31	6	-190	23	CHIX1	FLO70 -
131439		C196H	C	71	31	15	-191	23	CHIX1	5000 ft?
131943		C196I	C	71	31	18	-191	23	irn 45	Running
132121		C196J	C	71	31	19	-191	24	CHIX1	
132343		C196K	0	71	31	20	-191	24	Z30 x1	Forgot to open shutter - DOH!
132421		C196L	0	71	31	21	-191	24	Z30	
132536		C196M	C	71	31	21	-190	24	irn 45	Crash
1329										Res 16 cm ⁻¹ 24/s
134510		C196N	C	71	31	17	-190	25	ir - fast	ship? 5000 ft
134650		C196O	C	71	31	17	-190	25	ch1	
134720		C196P	C	71	31	17	-190	25	ir - fast	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B196

Location: Sen

page 4 of 5

Date: 10/5/06

Operator(s): TUDDEMAN / VANCE

Resolution: 16

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
135039	sun	C196 Q	C	71	31	16	-190	24	ir - fast	5000ft
135270		C196 R	C	71	31	16	-190	24	chl x 1	
140100	200ft run	C196 S	C	71	31	19	-191	26	ir - fast	2000ft
140250		C196 T	C	71	31	19	-190	26	fr - fast chl	
1408		C196 U	C						ir - fast	ABORTED
14		C196 V	C						ir - fast	?
141300		C196 W	C	71	31	19	-190	26	ir - fast	
141631		C196 X	C	71	32	21	-191	26	ir - fast	ship
141811		C196 Y	C	71	31	22	-191	26	chl x 1	
141842		C196 Z	C	71	30	22	-191	26	ir - fast	ship
142024		C196 0	C	71	31	22	-190	27	chl x 1	
142330	100ft Run	C196 1	C	71	31	22	-190	27	NI x 2	100ft Res back to 1cm ⁻¹
142530		C196 2	C	71	31	21	-191	27	CHL x 1	
142632		C196 3	C	71	31	21	-190	27	NI x 2	
142855		C196 4	C	70	31	20	-190	26	ZI x 1	
143101		C196 5	C	71	31	19	-190	26	CHL x 1	
143210		C196 6	C	71	31	19	-191	27	NI x 1	
143459	150ft Run	C196 7	C	71	31	19	-190	26	CHL x 1	Crossed
144039		C196 8	C	71	31	19	-190	27	CHL x 1	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	10/05/06	Flight	B196	log pages	2
Operator(s)	Chawn Harlow		Campaign	CAESAR/VisUrb			
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers	
FERA on	at time 08:13:17
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16 22°C Ch 23°C Ch18 20°C
Temperature controller set points	54°C 17 58°C -20 40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time 08:14:05
Initial target temperatures	Hot 290 Cold 290
Target heating	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***	
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time 08:18:08
Scan indication	Monitor Visual

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	
Turn on Deimos CPU	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***	
Start Deimos Software	at time
Initial target temperatures	Hot Cold
Target heating	
Scan indication	Monitor Visual
Weather	Cloud none Precip none Surface dry Pressure high Other

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	09:03:30	
Brightness temps 'sensible'					
Target temps	MARSS: Hot 345 Cold 292				
	Deimos: Hot Cold				
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A (-)	Ch3 A (-)	Ch1 B (-)	Ch3 B (-)	
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)
	42.5	34.8	38.4	41.9	42.8

Power changeover

Headset on before start	
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)	
Exit Deimos Software (x)	
POWER CHANGEOVER	
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton
Restart Deimos Software	
System running again	at time
	10:39:30

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.196**.....

 Date 10/5/06.....

 Operator's name: SB.....

 Page 1 of 2.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks						
								T _w	DRY	WET	Flow			
0959		GROUND	STATE				15.0	20.0	50.3	70.6	46.4	70.0	62.0	11.3
11:22								PC LOCKED UP ON TAKE OFF/PWR C/O JUST BACK UP.						
								ALL BACK OK						
							↑36							
11:26							↑40	34.9	RHS @ 96%					
11:27							↓35		" " To HSH					
11:40							↑37.5	35	" " ≈90 -So FOR 95					
11:50							↑39	37.5	" " " " " "					
11:56									RHS @ 3000ft - will ramp RH.					
11:57							↓15	39						
12:01:36							↑40	17.4	PB To 5000ft HEIGHT CHANGE TO OPEN TO RAMP RH.					
12:16									P4 To 2000ft RH.					
12:27									W:D QUITE NOISY - DIFFICULT TO SURSE GROWTH RATE					
12:55							↓39	40	RHS @ 98%					
13:00							↑39.5	39						
13:12							↓38.0	39.5	RHS @ 97%					
13:24:14							↓38.5	39	RHS @ 96.7%					
13:28:21							↓38	38.5	" " 97%					
13:41							↑39	38	" " 90%					
13:56:30							↑39.5	39	" " 89%					

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 016	Date	10/5/06	Operator(s)	Wilson	log page	(of)
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks NEON FLIGHT.			
				Vis	NIR				

						SWS BEING RUN.			
						<u>NO</u> SHIMS DATA THIS FLIGHT.			
110000Z	TRANSIT		0°	200	2000	DARK then measure.			
111701Z	P1		180						
111750			180	200	750	dark			
111815	P093		180	200	750	measure			
112749			180°	200	500	dark			
112759	1000ft		180°	200	500	measure			
113435	500ft	R1.1		200	500	runway pass (offset)			
113459						end runway			
11392514	R1.2	500ft	180°	200	500°	start runway pass			
11395833						end runway pass (offset)			
114601	R2.1	1000ft	180°	200	500	start runway pass @ 1000ft			
114648						end.			
115259	R2.2	1000ft	180	200	500	start runway pass @ 1000ft.			
115332						end pass.			
115359	P2	1000ft ↑	180	200	500.	Start P2 → 3000ft			
115548	P2	3000ft.				end P2 @ 3000ft			
115700						V. Loud shouting (!!) noises heard from Aries operator. (AK Vance.)			
120016Z	R3.1	3000ft	180°	200	500	start R3.1 runway overpass (offset)			
120049Z	R3.1					end R3.1			
120136Z	P3	3000ft ↑				start P3 → 5000ft			
120345Z	P3	5000ft	180	200	500	end P3 @ 5000ft.			
120438		5000ft		200	500	dark			
120456			180	200	500	measure			
120817	R4.1	5000ft	180°	200	500	Start R4.1			
120857						End R4.1			
121553	P4		---	---	---	start P4			
121900	P4	8000ft				end P4			
122405	R5.1	8000ft	180	200	500	start R5.1			
122448						end R5.1			
123204Z	R5.2	FLO80	---	---	---	start R5.2 @ FLO80			
123319Z	R5.2					end R5.2			
123635Z	P5	FLO80 ↑	180	200	500	start P5 → FLO80			
						SWS left running. unattended.			
						Further DATA NOT required.			
152300						DATA STOP!			

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 196 Date: 10th May 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	N	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	N
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
		AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	Y	<u>Others:</u>	
DEIMOS	N	IR Camera	Y
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	N	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	Noxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B196

Date: 10 May 2006

Instruments

1. Ufc & dfc videos hunt for correct exposure
2. HORACE derived data y vs x plots not displaying
3. ARIES intermittent faults

Aircraft

1. inboard comms box on ssp 7 u/s

Satcom Calls

Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B196:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath locating
Cloud Physics processing	Awaiting Jamie Trembath processing
CCN	Bruce Giddings locating
Core Chemistry	NO log taken - replaced by post flight auto cal removal
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
IR camera	Joss Kent locating
IR Camera Processing log	IR Camera Processing log not currently available

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	26 Sep 2006	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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